

BIBLIOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEM

Journal Full Title: [Journal of Biomedical Research & Environmental Sciences](#)

Journal NLM Abbreviation: J Biomed Res Environ Sci

Journal Website Link: <https://www.jelsciences.com>

Journal ISSN: 2766-2276

Category: Multidisciplinary

Subject Areas: Medicine Group, Biology Group, General, Environmental Sciences

Topics Summation: 130

Issue Regularity: [Monthly](#)

Review Process: [Double Blind](#)

Time to Publication: 21 Days

Indexing catalog: [Visit here](#)

Publication fee catalog: [Visit here](#)

DOI: 10.37871 ([CrossRef](#))

Plagiarism detection software: [iThenticate](#)

Managing entity: USA

Language: English

Research work collecting capability: Worldwide

Organized by: [SciRes Literature LLC](#)

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Manuscript should be submitted in Word Document (.doc or .docx) through

Online Submission

form or can be mailed to support@jelsciences.com

**IndexCopernicus
ICV 2020:
53.77**

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COMMENTARY

Research Project on the Real Effectiveness and Impact of Vaccination Against Rotavirus Diarrhea in DR Congo

Christophe Luhata Lungayo^{1,2*}, Rachel Burke³, John Samuel Otomba⁹, Odile Launay⁷ and Romain Jouffroy²⁻⁶

¹Expanded Programme on Immunization (EPI), Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of Congo

²INSERM U-1018, Centre de recherche en Épidémiologie et Santé des Populations - U1018 INSERM, Université Paris Saclay, Paris, France

³Intensive Care Unit, Ambroise Paré Hospital, Assistance Publique - Hôpitaux de Paris, Paris, France

⁴IRMES - Institute for Research in Medicine and Epidemiology of Sport, INSEP, Paris, France

⁵EA 7329, Université de Paris, Paris, France

⁶EA 7525 Université des Antilles, Pointe-Pitre, France

⁷Université Paris Descartes, Sorbonne Paris cité, and Inserm CIC 1417, F-CRIN I-Reivac, Assistance Publique Hôpitaux de Paris, CIC Cochin-Pasteur, Paris, France

⁸Viral Gastroenteritis Branch, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, Atlanta, Georgia

⁹World Health Organization Country Office of DRC, Democratic Republic of the Congo

INTRODUCTION

Vaccination is one of the most effective investments in public health. It contributes to the significant reduction of diseases and long-term disabilities [1]. Thus, several vaccines have been used for several decades in different countries. Their main expected impact is to significantly reduce mortality and morbidity due to the infectious diseases they target and thus save millions of human lives.

Although the proofs of efficacy of these different vaccines (Efficacy) have always been demonstrated during randomized controlled clinical trials under ideal conditions, thus allowing their approval or their marketing, many questions about the efficacy of the vaccine in the real conditions (Effectiveness) can only be given by observational approaches after the use of the vaccine [2]. This is because the results of randomized trials do not take into account certain real conditions of their use which may be either related to vaccines (vaccine storage conditions, observance of dosage, route of administration, number doses and intervals required between doses, etc.), or related to the host (age at the time of vaccination, genetic factors, immunosuppression, nutritional status, comorbidities, etc.) which can modify the immune response and vaccine efficacy in certain populations [3-5]. In addition, herd immunity is also not taken into account, which may lead to an underestimation of the overall effect of the vaccine in the population. This is why once large-scale vaccination has started, it is recommended to document its effectiveness in the field to determine the protection conferred by the vaccine in a population under real conditions of use "Effectiveness" [6,7].

A quick review of the literature on the real effectiveness of available vaccines against rotavirus diarrhea provides the following information. Overall, Rotarix and Rota Teq reduce the risk of hospitalization due to rotavirus-associated

*Corresponding author

Christophe Luhata Lungayo, Expanded Programme on Immunization (EPI), Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of Congo & Centre de recherche en épidémiologie et santé des populations (CESP), INSERM U1018, Paris, France, B.P. 11850 Kin I

Tel: +243-815-250040 (DR Congo) & +33-758-778727 (France)

E-mail: christophe.luhata@pevrdrcongo.cd

DOI: 10.37871/jbres1441

Submitted: 24 March 2022

Accepted: 04 April 2022

Published: 05 April 2022

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BIOLOGY GROUP

VACCINES | BIOLOGY

VOLUME: 3 ISSUE: 4 - APRIL, 2022

gastroenteritis by nearly 70% in fully immunized children, while Rotavac and Rotasiil show a moderate reduction in the risk of hospitalization due to gastroenteritis associated with rotavirus around 30% [8]. In Africa, vaccination with four vaccines currently prequalified by WHO (Rotarix, RotaTeq, Rotavac and RotaSiil) contributes to the reduction of approximately 40% of hospitalizations due to rotavirus-associated gastroenteritis in children under 5 years after the introduction of the vaccine for the period from 2006 to 2018 [9]. Considering some countries taken individually, we note for example that in Rwanda, a complete series of 3 doses was 75% effective against gastrointestinal -rotavirus enteritis requiring hospitalization or a visit to a health center in children and in Malawi, the estimated effective vaccine against rotavirus transmission was 39% [10,11].

In the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), the Expanded Vaccination Program (EPI) was set up in 1978 with the mission of contributing to better survival of the mother-child couple by reducing morbidity and mortality due to diseases Vaccine-preventable. The country introduced the rotavirus diarrhea vaccine "Rotasiil" in October 2019 [12,13]. It is important to note that the introduction of the Rotasiil vaccine was 10 years after the establishment of surveillance in Rotavirus gastroenteritis sentinel sites which revealed that 61% of diarrhea in children aged 0 to 5 years was caused by Rotavirus for data collected from August 2009 to June 2012 [14].

Although post-introduction vaccine impact and efficacy data for Rotavirus diarrhea vaccine (in monovalent and pentavalent vaccines) are available at the global level, at the level of the African region and for some African countries, but the Democratic Republic of Congo does not yet have these very useful data. However, the many challenges facing the vaccination system suggest that they would have an influence on the effectiveness of vaccines administered in the DRC: The EGEV shows that the score of the cold chain equipment temperature monitoring criterion does not is only 55% nationwide. The temperature readings and alarms are not subject to evaluation and analysis by the service providers and, consequently, there is no recording of these results nor any taking of corrective measures in a register. In addition, some nurses in health centers do not know the recommended temperature ranges for storing vaccines and do not know how to correctly fill in temperature sheets [15]. In terms of nutritional status, the DHS survey shows that among children under 6 months the proportion of children with growth retardation is 15% and that of those with the severe form of Chronic malnutrition is increasing and exceeds 7%, while 11% of children under 12 months suffer from acute malnutrition [16]. In addition to these two considerations, other situations, even if they are not precisely quantified, are not negligible in their possibilities of influencing vaccine efficacy, including: non-compliance with appointment intervals for taking vaccines represented by a considerable proportion of children recovered by

community relays; the proportion of immunosuppression by HIV or other causes as well as ethnic diversity which may reflect genetic diversity.

This is why we wish, through this research project, to evaluate the real effectiveness (Effectiveness) and the impact of vaccination against Rotavirus diarrhea in order to assess the contribution of the vaccination program according to the mission assigned to it. assigned in the DRC.

This research project aims to answer these questions:

- What is the real level of effectiveness of the Rotasiil vaccine administered in the DR Congo?
- What are the factors explaining this level of real effectiveness of the Rotasiil vaccine administered in the D.R. Congo?
- What is the impact of vaccination on the disease and changes in epidemiology and circulating strains after the introduction of rotavirus vaccine in DR Congo?

RATIONALE FOR THIS PROJECT

In October 2019, the Democratic Republic of the Congo introduced the Rotasiil vaccine into the vaccination schedule for children aged 0 to 11 months given in i.e., 10 years after setting up sentinel site surveillance with the aim of contributing to reducing the burden of morbidity and mortality due to Rotavirus gastroenteritis. Carrying out this research project will allow the country, in addition to the general objectives of surveillance of rotavirus infection, to achieve the 2 specific objectives of this surveillance when à country has already introduced à rotavirus vaccine into the vaccination schedule. Which are: 1. To monitor the impact of vaccination on disease and changes in epidemiology and circulating strains following the introduction of rotavirus vaccine; 2. Assess the effectiveness of vaccines using surveillance as a platform for special studies [17]. This will make it possible to assess the contribution of the vaccination program according to the mission assigned to it and also help to strengthen the implementation of surveillance.

Goals

We set ourselves two objectives for the realization of this research:

First, to determine the real vaccine effectiveness (Effectiveness) after the introduction of Rotasiil in the vaccination schedule in force in the D.R. Congo.

Second, to determine the impact of vaccination against rotavirus diarrhea on the epidemiology of the disease and the viral epidemiology after its introduction in the D.R. Congo.

REFERENCES

1. Gavi. The Vaccines Alliance (Gavi, Apr 2018).

2. Lipsitch M, Jha A, Simonsen L. Observational studies and the difficult quest for causality: lessons from vaccine effectiveness and impact studies. *Int J Epidemiol.* 2016;45(6):2060-2074. doi:10.1093/ije/dyw124
3. World Health Organization (WHO) Immunization, vaccines and biological.
4. Immunology of vaccination. <https://bit.ly/3uWI51w>
5. Ramani S, Giri S. Influence of histo blood group antigen expression on susceptibility to enteric viruses and vaccines. *Curr Opin Infect Dis.* 2019 Oct;32(5):445-452. doi: 10.1097/QCO.0000000000000571.
6. "Efficacy and effectiveness | Immunisation Advisory Centre. <https://bit.ly/3r3z0lb>
7. Germaine Hanquet, MartaValenciano, FrançoisSimondon, AlainMoren. Vaccine effects and impact of vaccination programmes in post-licensure studies. 2013;31(48):5634-5642
8. Sun ZW, Fu Y, Lu HL, Yang RX, Goyal H, Jiang Y, Xu HG. Association of Rotavirus vaccines with reduction in Rotavirus gastroenteritis in children younger than 5 Years: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis of Randomized Clinical Trials and Observational Studies. *JAMA Pediatr.* 2021 Jul 1;175(7):e210347. doi: 10.1001/jamapediatrics.2021.0347.
9. Mphahlele MJ, Groome MJ, Page NA, Bhagwandin N, Mwenda JM, Steele AD. A decade of rotavirus vaccination in Africa - Saving lives and changing the face of diarrhoeal diseases: Report of the 12th African Rotavirus Symposium. *Vaccine.* 2021 Apr 22;39(17):2319-2324. doi: 10.1016/j.vaccine.2021.03.014.
10. Tate JE, Ngabo F, Donnen P, Gatera M, Uwimana J, et al. Effectiveness of Pentavalent Rotavirus vaccine under conditions of routine use in Rwanda. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2016 May 1;62 Suppl 2:S208-12. doi: 10.1093/cid/civ1016.
11. Bennett A, Pollock L, Bar-Zeev N, Lewnard JA, Jere KC, Lopman B, Iturriza-Gomara M, Pitzer VE, Cunliffe NA. Community transmission of rotavirus infection in a vaccinated population in Blantyre, Malawi: a prospective household cohort study. *Lancet Infect Dis.* 2021 May; 21(5):731-740. doi: 10.1016/S1473-3099(20)30597-1.
12. Ministère de la Santé, Plan Pluriannuel Complet du PEV-R.D. Congo 2015-2019. 2015.
13. Ministère de la Santé, Plan Pluriannuel Complet du PEV-R.D. Congo 2020-2024. 2020.
14. Pukuta ES, Esona MD, Nkongolo A, Seheri M, Makasi M, et al. SURVAC Working Group. Molecular surveillance of rotavirus infection in the Democratic Republic of the Congo August 2009 to June 2012. *Pediatr Infect Dis J.* 2014 Apr;33(4):355-9. doi: 10.1097/INF.0000000000000212.
15. Ministère du Plan et Suivi de la Mise en œuvre de la Révolution de la Modernité (MPSMRM); Ministère de la Santé Publique (MSP); ICF International. Enquête Démographique et de Santé en République Démocratique du Congo 2013–2014. Rockville, MD: MPSMRM, MSP, and ICF International. 2014.
16. Ministère de la Santé, Evaluation de Gestion efficace des vaccins, PEV-RDC. 2019.
17. Patel MM, Parashar UD. Assessing the effectiveness and public health impact of rotavirus vaccines after introduction in immunization programs. *J Infect Dis.* 2009 Nov 1;200 Suppl 1:S291-9. doi: 10.1086/605059.

How to cite this article: Lungayo CL, Burke R, Otomba JS, Launay O, Jouffroy R. Research Project on the Real Effectiveness and Impact of Vaccination Against Rotavirus Diarrhea in DR Congo. *J Biomed Res Environ Sci.* 2022 Apr 05; 3(4): 320-322. doi: 10.37871/jbres1441, Article ID: JBRES1441, Available at: <https://www.jelsciences.com/articles/jbres1441.pdf>